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Student Assessed Impact of Active Learning Methods and Andragogy

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ABSTRACT

This research work is aimed at demonstrating active learning techniques and soliciting student input on their effectiveness. Active methods of teaching stimulate the thinking of students and are characterized by a high degree of motivation and emotional engagement in the learning process. That is why active forms of training can provide a more complete inclusion of students in the learning process and a more effective transfer of knowledge. This paper reports on a course for organizing and planning a chemical laboratory in which a variety of active learning techniques were applied. A team project provided the continuous thread on which to apply the course content. Individual and collaborative assignments supported the team project and gave the course a highly inter-active structure. Following the course, the students responded to two written surveys and a guided discussion session to explore the impact of this approach. Overall, the active learning approach was viewed very positively by 2 out of 3 students. However some students pointed out that this approach required more effort and time from them and therefore was not preferred.

1 INTRODUCTION

At present, scientists are very interested in the challenges of modern engineering education, as evidenced by numerous international forums and conferences that gather a huge number of scientists interested in this problem [1]. While lifelong learning is essential to professional growth, the motivation and knowledge necessary for a person at every stage of his life changes. The main challenge for the educator is not only to assimilate this constantly increasing volume of knowledge, but to integrate this knowledge into technical areas that did not previously exist. Furthermore, the professional engineer must recognize that this new knowledge is important and it is necessary to keep current with new developments. Rapid obsolescence of scientific information makes it necessary to search for new sources of knowledge and to form skills around this knowledge in real production situations. The newly acquired design skills should facilitate the timely adaptation of a specialist to changing production tasks [2].

The development of the economy of any state is not possible without continuous advanced training of specialists in the field of technology and technology capable of solving the tasks of innovative development. This training must take into account not only the current needs, but also the long-term needs of industry and society as a whole. This means that future engineers must continuously grow new competencies allowing them to set and solve new tasks, and offer innovative engineering solutions [3].

Universities have defined a set of key competences (professional and societal) that a graduate must possess for satisfactory completion of an educational curriculum [4]. However, industry often expresses dissatisfaction with the quality of training received by new engineers, noting that the level of the formation of key competencies is insufficient for many new graduates to carry out complex engineering activities without a long period of adaptation and additional maturation. In addition to technical knowledge, other skills such as communication, teamwork, problems solving and life-long learning are critical to success in the technical world.

In present day Russian engineering education, there are both systemic and social obstacles within the engineering education community to achieving these learning outcomes:

- Failure to acknowledge that graduates are not meeting expectations,
- Failure to recognize that the learning outcomes include more than technical knowledge but must include psychological and social skills.
- Failure to acknowledge the deficiencies in the traditional pedagogical approaches in achieving the full spectrum of these learning outcomes
- Resistance by the university faculty to adopt modern learning technologies needed for the new generation of learners.
- Failure by the university structure to drive the change that is needed.

The application of active teaching methods can play an important role in overcoming these issues. The most prevalent teaching methods in Russian pedagogy is lecture, test work, independent work, test, oral questioning, story, explanation, exercise, laboratory work and practical exercises. Most often, the teaching is unidirectional presentation of content. Active teaching methods, on the other hand, require the student to participate in the learning process. Typical activities include problem-based lectures, lectures with pre-planned errors, interactive and visually stimulating presentation of material (accompanying lecture with slide presentation, information stand, illustrations, posters), student-teacher inquiry-based discussions, business game, brainstorming, and open ended laboratory activities with group discussion and assessments. The goal of these activities are to bring students into the context of their future professional life.

2 APPROACH

This study involved 50 undergraduate, fourth year, students majoring in polymer engineering. These students were predominantly traditional students ranging in age from 22-23 years old and enrolled in a course entitled "Organization and Planning of the Operation of Chemical Laboratories". Many of the students are already working in industry and this class was given in two classes with one being in the evening. The context of this chemical laboratory to support the production of rubber including processing, additives, and vulcanization. The syllabus of this course covers a wide range of topics applicable to the operation of a chemical laboratory including fire safety, personnel protection, storage, treatment and recycling of reagents, containers and glassware, ventilation, work organization and planning. In previous years of their study, the students rarely encountered active teaching methods with the most frequent method being the traditional lecture.

A collaborative team project was the key learning thread in the course. This team project is supported throughout the course by both individual and collaborative assignments. A project was created that applies the principles of laboratory organization to a specific chemical laboratory situation upon which the specific course topics can be applied. The same project topic was given to the whole class and the class was divided into subgroups/teams in accordance with the number of stages of production. After dividing into groups, the students received a set of recommended readings from the literature. Students independently studied the production schema in accordance with the received tasks followed by group discussion. The group created a schematic diagram of their specific production stage. At this point, students saw the composition and structure of the whole production process.

The next stage of the project took the form of an instructor-guided seminar. The subject of the seminars was some aspect of rubber processing derived from the project focus. The lecturer acted as a coach and therefore did not interfere in the discussion, impose an opinion or correct errors. Note that if students have chosen a wrong course for the technological process, the analysis revealed this error in the

subsequent course work at which time the group must correct them. Based on the results of the seminar-discussion, the instructor issued an assignment to the subgroup to perform the technical calculations of each separate stage, and assigned each student to the technical calculation of a particular apparatus. In effect, the lecturer served as project administrator but did not give technical direction. [Note that these students have not been given any formal training in project management, an issue for another discussion]. Each student provided technical calculations that confirmed satisfactorily meeting regulatory requirements.

The next phase of the project focused on the graphical design of each stage of production. Brainstorming took place on possible design solutions where each student acted both as a generator of ideas and as a critic. As the team approached the preparation of the graphics for the project, students came together and agreed on the development of the graphic part of the production process. When safety and personnel protection was treated in the course, each student prepared a presentation and a report on his/her part of the technological scheme. Finally the whole team discussed the merits and weaknesses of the developed technological scheme of production.

This integrated approach of progressive, project development applying course subject matter to the project scenario creates a model with the real world context of today's engineering world. The goal of this approach was to stimulate the thinking of students, to push them to seek additional information in literary and internet-sources, and to contribute to the development of engineering thinking of the future specialist.

3 STUDENT ASSESSMENT OF ACTIVE LEARNING

The primary focus of this paper is on gathering and evaluating student opinions on the active learning techniques used in the course. The impact of active learning techniques in this course from the student point of view was evaluated using two written, multiple choice surveys and a recorded, instructor guided, oral group discussion.

3.1 Impact on Learning

The first survey is shown in Table 1 and explores the impact of the active learning approaches. This sixteen-question survey is divided into three thematic groups regarding impact of the active learning methods: 1) impact on learning 2) impact on interpersonal interactions and 3) impact on knowledge retention. 100% of the respondents gave answers to all questions of the questionnaire.

Regarding the impact to learning, the students expressed good support (approximately 75% of the students) for the ease of understanding, recalling, and reproducing the content of the course (questions 2,3,4). Furthermore, improved attention and interest in the class was also evidenced by the same percentage in question 5.

Survey 1 Questions				
Functionality of Active Learning Methods	Strongly Disagree, %	Disagree, %	Agree, %	Strongly agree, %
1. Are the active teaching methods used in the course relevant?	0	0	0	100
2. Is it easier for you to understand the material of the lecture course if it is accompanied by a slide presentation, information stand, illustrations, posters, group discussions, brainstorming sessions?	8	15	25	47
3. Is it easier to remember the material of the lecture course if it is accompanied by a slide presentation, information stand, illustrations, posters, group discussions, brainstorming sessions?	4	20	30	46
4. Is it easier for you to reproduce the material received in the classroom if its central positions and problems were discussed in group discussions, business games, seminars, practical and experimental studies?	16	10	30	44
5. Are you more interested in classes that take place in active and interactive modes (problem lecture, practice, group discussions, group discussions, experiment) in comparison with classical lectures, practical exercises, laboratory work?	10	18	32	40
Influence of Active Learning methods on Improving of Ability to Interpersonal Interactions				
6. Do you observe the improvement of individual cognitive activity in discipline due to participation in active studies?	7	40	15	38
7. Do you observe the improvement in academic performance by participating in active studies?	10	40	10	40
8. Does participation in problem (active) classes develop a sense of responsibility to a greater extent than classical ones?	10	54	3	33
9. Do these classes develop a sense of self-confidence and their own strength in comparison with the classical ones?	26	50	2	22
10. Do active activities develop friendly feelings for classmates?	2	20	3	75
11. Do the activities develop friendly feelings for the teacher?	24	50	1	25
12. Do they bring up a feeling of respect and tolerance to someone else's opinion?	6	10	4	80
13. Do active classes contribute to the development of professional qualities, skills, and abilities to a greater extent than classical methods of teaching?	10	62	2	26
Impact of Active Learning Methods on Knowledge Retention				
14. Do you think effective methods of training are effective?	6	30	2	62
15. In your opinion, does the use of active teaching methods promote the increase in the effectiveness of the educational process, along with classical methods?	6	30	2	62
16. Do you think there is a need to use active teaching methods in the educational process, along with the classical ones?	4	30	0	66

Table 1. The results of a student survey regarding the impact of active techniques on student learning (self-assessment). The dominant opinion direction is shaded.

The impact of the active learning on personal performance was mixed and not as strong, with only 50% of the class observing improvement. Only a third (36%) of the students felt that they gained a sense of responsibility or self-confidence from the active learning approach as compared to the traditional lecture. On the other hand, the students expressed a strong improvement in their appreciation and respect for their classmates (78% and 84% respectively in questions 10 and 12). Not surprisingly, only 26% of the students felt the relationship with their instructor was improved since most of the active technologies adopted in this research takes the focus off the instructor and onto their classmates in a collaborative manner. In

question 13, the vast majority of the students (72%) did not recognize that their interpersonal skills were an integral part of their required professional skills and they will be important in their professional lives. In future surveys, the wording of this question will be improved since the topic may not have been sufficient clear.

Finally, the students confirmed their feelings (2 to 1) that the active learning approaches that were used in this course were effective and would enhance the effectiveness of the traditional lectures approach. Nevertheless, the support for active learning was not unanimous. Reasons for this will be discussed in the following sections.

3.2 Preferred Active Learning Techniques

The second, eight question survey explores the student’s preferences on specific active learning techniques and methods. The survey and the student responses are shown in table 2.

The most preferred method of lecture, for 54% of respondents in question 2, was the lecture-presentation. This mode of lecture allows focusing on the main material of

Survey 2	
Survey Questions	Response, %
1. Rank the presented active forms of conducting classes relative to those you liked and remembered more, 10 being the most liked	
a) experiment	18
b) lecture-presentation	18
c) demonstration / practice	12
d) brainstorming	6
e) business games	8
e) problem lecture	2
g) student-teacher	10
h) lectures with pre-planned errors	10
i) workshop	10
j) small circles of knowledge (group discussion)	6
2. What method of lecture do you like more?	
a) a classical lecture	33
b) problem lecture	14
c) lecture-presentation.	54
3. What method of intermediate knowledge control do you like more?	
a) test	68
c) oral interview	12
d) colloquium	10
e) lecture with errors.	10
4. What form of practical and experimental activities do you like more?	
a) active (practice, experiment with group and individual discussion of problem situations);	44
b) passive (practical and laboratory work of a standard type).	56
5. Which teaching method allows you to fully represent your point of view in a problem situation?	
a) brainstorming	14
b) group discussions	76
c) business game	10
6. In what kind of classes are you most interested in presenting the material to the whole group, to make a report?	
a) seminar;	10
b) student-teacher;	10
c) group discussion;	55
d) do not like to submit the material yourself.	25
7. Which of the training methods has the most motivating effect on you? Select one.	
a) classical	34
b) active.	66
If you chose position b), then answer the following question:Which of the active teaching methods has the most motivating effect (develops motivation for learning)?	
a) experiment	16
b) demonstration / practice	6
c) brainstorming	14
d) business games	2
e) problem lecture	10
f) student-teacher coaching	14
g) lectures with pre-planned errors	2
h) seminar /working session	24
i) small circles of knowledge	12
8. Is it worthwhile to apply active teaching methods or is it better to conduct classes using the classical method?	
a) it is worthwhile to introduce active teaching methods;	58
b) classes will be more effective when using classical techniques.	42

Table 2. A student survey regarding their preferences of active learning techniques

the lecture enhanced with tables, diagrams, explanatory drawings and drawings. This lecture type was preferred over the verbal only lecture prevalent at this institution. The most challenging problem lecture format was least preferred.

These results might be explained as follows. For students who want to understand the material of the lecture, it is most effective to obtain the information in a succinct but informative way (with visual presentation slides). Classical lecture provides a large amount of undigested material while a problem lecture requires more involved student participation in the lecture and discussion of the problem.

The most preferred form of knowledge assessment/exam was the classic test with 68% favourable. Lecture with errors and oral/colloquium type exams selected by only of respondents respectively. This preference is understandable since students find it easier to feedback lecture information rather than have to formulate a response in their own words. The use of a lecture with pre-planned errors does not enjoy the success of the adult student environment possibly because this method is not yet widespread and is more challenging. Oral exam formats are less predictable than the standard written formats.

Practical, laboratory exercises are an essential component of the student's learning activity. For traditional classes, students perform the assigned tasks individually and present a conclusion in the form of a report. In the active approach, after completing the technique or experiment, students discussed the results in small groups, drew the main conclusions and defended them in front of the whole group. The passive or individual method was favoured 56% to 44%. The preference for individual activities, whose results are not dependant on other students, is quite common among students particularly the higher performing students.

The ability of a student to justify his own opinion is an important personal skill. According to respondents in both question 5 (76%) and question 6 (55%) , group discussions allow to fully disclose the individual attitude of each student to the question posed, to prove one's own point of view in the problem situation, to justify the idea of solving the problem, or to develop these abilities. From question 6, it is clear that a significant portion of the class (25%) may not be confident in their presentation abilities. This suggests that this is an area for intentional improvement perhaps not just in this class but also within the entire curriculum.

Active methods of training, of course, are able to motivate students to a successful educational process. It is also interesting to find out which of the active forms of training are of the greatest motivating nature and contribute to the work of the students involved. The responses from question 1 and 8 have been examined together in order to get a more coherent picture.

Clearly, the hands-on dimension of experiment and seminar/workshop resonated with the students and this result was satisfying for the instructors since this type of hands-on pedagogy requires more instructor effort. Participating in a seminar, delivering a report and presentation to classmates, sharing their own experience are critical communication skills and highly desirable in the workplace. The second tier of

preference were four activities: student/teacher interaction, brainstorming, small group discussions and demonstration. The least favoured approaches were the problem lecture, business games and lecture with errors.

Overall, it can be concluded that the most motivating methods of active learning for this class are hands-on and inter-personal participatory orientated. By active participation in the classes students are rewarded and credited with points that form an individual rating system.

3.3 Instructor Guided Oral Discussion

Finally, in this research, a recorded, instructor guided, oral group discussion was used to clarify the student's views on the effectiveness of the active learning methods. The conversation was held at one of the final seminar sessions in a lecture room in an atmosphere of mutual trust. The answers of students were recorded, analysed, structured and summarized. The discussion was structured with specific questions to stimulate student responses.

1) Do you consider the active teaching methods used in the discipline in question relevant and why?

Participant opinions were divided on this question.

On the positive side:

"We believe that the use of active forms of education is really important, as they make it easier and more productive to learn the material, less time to learn it"

"These classes encourage students to work through participation in the work of reflection groups and making presentations. In addition, in the discussion groups it does not matter whose answer is more accurate".

"It is important to take into account the opinions of each on the question posed and the ability to prove their point of view.

From the negative side.

"For us, the traditional methods of classical training are more relevant, since active forms of instruction require increased attention, greater participation, and take more preparation time. It should be remembered, though, that we are a group of the evening department and sometimes come to classes already tired. For example, it is easier to prepare for a test or a colloquium than do the same actions, supplementing them with the preparation of seminar reports and reports for the "student-teacher" form in their spare time".

From the instructor's point of view, the question becomes whether the learning outcomes were better achieved. Often students are not interested in increasing their workload even though they will have learned better and more. Unfortunately, an assessment of the preparedness of these students relative to others was not available.

2) Due to what factors does your cognitive activity and degree of interest increase with participation in active forms of learning?

“Accompanying the lecture with examples from life and demonstrative posters, pictures, illustrations, sharpens attention and facilitates understanding of the material”.

“It is interesting to listen to...our classmates who have direct experience of work in this or that sphere, considered in the class as a topic.”

From an instructor’s point of view, this last comment serves an important academic function and answers the student’s question “Why am I learning this?” and the answer was coming from their cohort and fellow students.

3) Why do you think that active forms of education do NOT lead to increased sense of responsibility?

“We believe that active forms of training DO increase the responsibility, since students should perform more independent training at home. This takes time”.

“Much depends on the nature of the person: If the student is unprincipled... then he will not participate in the class, "just be left behind or follow along”.

“Active forms of education leads us to be more to responsible, have a sense of proper behavior, but so much depends on the moral qualities of the individual learner.”

4) How do you compare the lecture-(slide)presentation with the classical lecture?

“On the slides accompanying the lecture, the most important information is shown, pictures and illustrations allow you to better understand the essence of the topic”.

5) Indicate the positive or negative aspects of the multiple choice exams, the method of lecture with errors and essay exams.

“Multiple choice allows you to choose the answer option from the available ones. Even if the student does not know the exact answer to the question, then the method of logical thinking can come to finding (the correct answer)”.

“A lecture with pre-planned errors requires increased attention and a higher degree of intelligibility, accompanied by a joint analysis with the teacher and the team”.

“Essay exams requires the memorization of lecture material and the solution of problems that are easy or complex”.

6) Describe why you like/dislike the following methods of actively solving problem situations - brainstorming, group discussion, business game.

“Brainstorming involves collecting a certain number of ideas within the given time, requires a high degree of promptness, mental work, which in conditions of post-work time is difficult.

“Group discussion allows the group to find or suggest ways to solve the problem and justify its choice to other participants in the communication groups. It’s easier to work in a group than independently.”

“Business games, in our opinion, are not an appropriate form of training for older part-time students (example when the student is working, 35-40 years old). This form of training would be more suitable for full-time younger students”.

7) Why are active forms of learning motivating / not motivating you to learn?

“Active forms of instruction motivate for training, since classes conducted in this form allow you to get more credit, provided you take a little more active participation, in comparison with the classical ones.

“Motivated, because you understand the course material easier and faster”

“(Active forms) do not motivate, because, when using active forms of education, students must spend more free time”.

The authors are not surprised by these last comments and they are consistent with the fact that almost 1/3 of the class still preferred the standard, spoon-fed lecture and multiple-choice exams. Students most commonly choose the easiest route but not the most productive one from the standpoint of learning.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes an implementation of active learning technologies in a course of “Organization and Planning of the Operation of Chemical Laboratories”. with a comprehensive suite of student feedback tools used to gather feedback: surveys, observation and personal interviews. This class with active learning methods elicited a strong positive response (2 to 1) from students, including effective collaboration with peers, development of teamwork skills and enhanced oral communication skills. The preferred techniques were lectures enhanced with visual stimuli, hands-on experimental work, and group discussions. For students, the benefit of this approach was the acquisition of technical knowledge in its applied context while experiencing decision-making, negotiating and working together. For teachers this approach required significant preparation, since it was necessary to develop a new teaching plan for the course, as well as new educational material. Because of this study, it is clear that there was not much gain in developing lectures with errors, and business games that are poorly received. However directing the development effort toward enhanced lectures, seminars and hands-on activities would be beneficial. Furthermore, the instructor had to learn the new role as mentor and facilitator.

Unfortunately the authors were unable, due to administrative constraints, to link a higher performance in the standard exams with this active form of teaching but look forward to connecting to this crucial, outcomes based comparison in future publications.

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